

The *Daimon* of the Interface: an (Alien) Phenomenological Approach to Writing Technology

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This is the text of the presentation I gave at the [Future of Writing symposium 2026](#). Since I do not think I am going to publish it in any academic journal, I'd rather make it public as a working paper, for those who could be interested in a phenomenological approach to teaching writing in time of Large Language Models.

“Our knowledge of reality is shaped by the tools and materials
we use to relate to the environment.”

(Laura Tripaldi,
Parallel Minds. Discovering the Intelligence of Materials,
Urbanomics, 2022)

Introduction

Digital writing has been the focus of my research since I started my PhD in 2020. In 2025 I published an adaptation of my PhD dissertation, under the title [Scritture digitali. Dai social media all'IA e all'editing genetico](#) ('Digital writing. From social media to AI to genetic editing', Meltemi, 2025) in which I develop a broad reflection about technology and writing (which is, as we all know, already a technology) and I try to understand how writing is changing now that it has gone digital. From human writing and its new forms to computer code, from synthetic text generated by LLMs to forms of genetic editing/writing such as CRISPR/Cas9, in the book I explore what writing has become and what it means in our digital age. In addition to research, I also work with the [Socialini](#) collective on digital literacy for middle school students. The ideas presented in this working paper are thus inspired both by my academic research and the digital literacy workshops I have led. I do not teach writing itself, but I came across many questions about writing both in my research work and in my teaching activity.

I intend the concept of “adaptability”, proposed as a theme for the Future of Writing symposium '26, in a double (and critical) sense: we can not ignore the new technologies coming onto the mass market and we have to understand their impact and their possible uses but, at the same time, we can work – as far as it is possible – to adapt technology and the use we make of it to our needs and goals rather than us having to adapt to tech market trends.

The method I present here is thus a hypothesis because I have not actually applied it to teaching, but I applied some aspects of it in teaching digital literacy, as I will explain. The goal of the workshops we lead with middle school students is to give them some basics elements of knowledge so they can move confidently through their digital lives, aware of what's going on and what is at stake. I think that some methods and ideas we use in teaching digital literacy can be applied to teaching writing as well.

While conducting our workshops, we realized that we cannot present ourselves in front of a middle school class pretending to tell them what is right and what is wrong in the way they already use digital devices and services, so we developed an approach that starts from their experience, their knowledge and their feelings, and we work with what emerges in the classroom, trying to mix it with our knowledge and the critical tools we can provide. For this approach, I am and we are in debt with the work of the [C.I.R.C.E. international collective](#), who suggests keeping a “squint look”, that is keeping at the same time an eye on the human and the other on the machine. So there is a little phenomenology involved, somehow on both sides.

Writing interfaces: find their *daimon*

In our workshops we use the interface analysis as proposed by the C.I.R.C.E. collective, an analysis which aims to understand what the software “wants” the users to do with it, what it pushes the user to do. The C.I.R.C.E. collective talks about the “daimon” of the interface: every app, every platform has its own temper, “an internal voice which guides the systems, a strong driving force in the interactions; not necessarily evil, even if the interaction can result toxic for us” (Fant – Milani, 2024). This approach underlines the fact that technology is never neutral, and it is important to analyze the tools, devices and platforms we use in order to understand how they are designed and how this design influences our behavior. The hacker pedagogy proposed by the C.I.R.C.E. collective (and that we use in our workshops) focuses mainly on social media and messaging apps, but my hypothesis is that we can do the same with writing tools. The interface analysis should be as less cognitive as possible: this means that the focus should be on the structure and not on the content. This way, we can force ourselves (and the students) to look at the interfaces with fresh eyes and to set aside acquired automatic gestures and responses.

Here is an example of how this analysis is conducted:

“Open WhatsApp! Let's begin our interface analysis. What do we see?”

“A flashing cursor.”

“Less cognitive. Who told you it's a cursor? What shape and color is it?”

“A narrow, vertical, light green rectangle that pulses.”

“The double check mark.”

“Less cognitive. Who told you it's a check mark if it's the first time you've seen it?

What shape and color is it?”

“A double ‘v’ that's longer on the right, blue.”

“A bar for writing a message.”

“Less cognitive. Let's say you can't read... how do you know it's for messages? What shape and color is it?”

“An elongated horizontal rectangle with sharply rounded corners, lighter than the background.” (Fant – Milani 2024)

This process makes it possible to highlight the elements that characterize the “daimon” of the app and understand the ways in which the app influence our behavior. If this is probably clearer and

more evident in social media and messaging app, I propose to apply this analysis to writing apps and interfaces in the classroom to make students more aware of what is involved in their writing, when they work on their assignments and when they write on their own. It could be part of preliminary lessons about writing, its meaning and the use of different writing tools. The analysis can bring the attention to very different tools: from “classic” Word to Google Docs and Cryptpad, from ChatGPT to Vim...

This first step will allow students to better understand the writing tools they use, getting to know what the machine “wants” from them by way of its design, and develop a critical approach to these tools. The second step brings the look on the human side of the process.

Writing humans: how do we feel while writing with different tools

The basic question of this part is “what happens in us while we use different tools for writing?”, which entails a phenomenological observation (and self-observation).

A first exercise might work like this: the teacher gives the students a writing assignment that must be repeated multiple times, each time using a different tool: it can start with writing by hand on a piece of paper, then move on to Word, then giving a prompt to a LLMs, then again writing with Vim. The process that this assignment should trigger is a form of meta-writing: while the students write they reflect on how they write and how they feel about their writing process. Ideally the work should be done in pairs or in very small groups (3 or 4 people maximum), so students can have enough time for the phenomenological observation. A set of questions should be presented beforehand to serve as a guide for the observation, so the students can ask them to one another. Possible questions can include: How do you feel when you are writing with this tool? What do you think about the resulting text? What are the positive aspects that you felt/experienced? What are the negative ones? Which text do you feel you remember better, and why is it so in your opinion? Which text do you identify with most? Anything else you would like to add about what you thought/felt while doing this exercise?

What did we learn?

The last step in this process should be a collective conversation where students and teachers share their experience, with a focus on the awareness they should have developed (or not?) about technology, writing and maybe themselves (in terms of their relationship with technology and writing).

If we understand the influence that a tool has on us, we can better choose which tools to use in our writing, depending on the needs, the assignment. But the goal of this method is to make students aware of the importance of the writing process and its strict correlation with thinking and how this process depends also on the tools they use.

As Vitali-Rosati writes, digital literacy is “perhaps one of the most important issues of our time. And understanding how digital space is made is not only a technical matter or a prerogative of

computer specialists: it is the condition of understanding our political situation. Digital space is the space where we live, it is the space where politics unfold: understanding it is therefore necessary for being a free and aware citizen” (Vitali-Rosati 2018). Since everything that happens in the digital environment is made of writing, be aware of the tools we use to create these forms of writing is indeed fundamental.

Essential bibliography

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